

CHAPTER 3

Investigation of structural, optoelectronic and thermoelectric properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$

To meet the demands of photovoltaic, thermoelectric, and other futuristic devices, multifunctional materials represent a thriving research area that both industrialists and academics are interested in. The versatility of multifunctionality allows simultaneous utilization of materials for two or more applications. Researchers from all over the world are attempting to boost the efficiency of sophisticated devices (spintronics-based, thermoelectric-based). To address these needs, several materials with various chemical compositions are being searched. Double perovskites ($\text{A}_2\text{BB}'\text{X}_6$) represent one group among such materials which can full fill the energy issue. However, explored $\text{A}_2\text{BB}'\text{X}_6$ double perovskite materials are not suitable for large scale commercialization because they are either suffering due to their poor stability or they do not have any promising optoelectronic properties. In this chapter, we have discussed about structural, electronic, optical and thermoelectric properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$. In first section, the structural properties such as crystal structure, lattice parameter, tolerance factor, octahedral factor and bond angle are calculated. In the next, thermodynamic stability of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$ are investigated by calculating their formation energy along with phonon band structure computation. Thereafter, the electronic properties such as band structure and density of states of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$ are discussed. Then we have discussed in details about the optical properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$. In the last section, we have discussed about the thermoelectric properties of these two compounds.

3.1 Simulation Details

The structural, electronic, optical and thermoelectric properties of title compounds were predicted by using the Wien2k simulation package [83]. The structural properties were calculated with the help of GGA-PBE exchange correlation , whereas to overcome the failure

of GGA-PBE in terms of accurate prediction of their band gaps, the new mBJ functional was taken into consideration [84]. It is important to mention here that the new mBJ can provide band gap value of lead-free double halide perovskite with the same accuracy as given by GW or hybrid functionals [83]. The plane wave cut-off i.e., product of maximum plane wave vector and smallest muffin-tin radius is used 8 ($K_{\max} * R_{\text{MT}} = 8.0$). In addition, the energy cut-off for geometry optimization was set to be 520 eV. Further, the average forces on ions were minimized to 0.002 eV/Å. Moreover, the electronic properties were investigated with k mesh of 10 X 10 X 10. We have obtained the level of 10^{-5} Ry convergence self consistently by using the above inputs. The thermoelectric properties were predicted by employing the BoltzTraP package [85]. It is worthy to mention that the optical and thermoelectric properties are sensitive to k-point sampling. Thus, we have considered a high dense k-points of 200000 to predict the same.

3.2.1 Structural properties

The structure $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ are crystalized in cubic phase with the Fm3m (No. 225) space group. The perspective view of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ structures are shown in figure 3.1 (a, b). It is noticeable from figure 3.1 (a, b) that $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ structures showed a network of corner sharing octahedra with Cs atoms located at the middle of the octahedral cavity. On the other hand, each Cs atom is coordinated with twelve I atoms whereas every Tl and (As/Sb) atoms are surrounded by six I atoms. Also, it is noticeable from figure 3.1 (a, b) that TlI_6 and $(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ octahedra are alternatively arranged along [1 0 0], [0 1 0] and [0 0 1] directions. The centre of each octahedron is alternatively occupied by Tl and (As/Sb) atoms in rock-salt configuration. Also, the Wyckoff positions of Cs is noticed to be at (0.25, 0.25, 0.25) whereas Tl, (As/Sb), and I atoms are positioned at (0.0, 0.0, 0.0), (0.5, 0.5, 0.5) and (0.24, 0.0, 0.0), respectively.

Cs ₂ TlAsI ₆	10.61	0.98	0.44	3.44	2.41	2.61	$\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^0$
Cs ₂ TlSbI ₆	10.66	0.98	0.43	3.41	2.44	2.65	$\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^0$

3.2.2 Stability analysis of Cs₂Tl(As/Sb)I₆

To investigate the thermodynamic stability of Cs₂Tl(As/Sb)I₆, we have further computed the formation energy (ΔE) by using the following equation

$$\Delta E = \frac{[E_{tot} - \sum_0^p n E^i]}{N} \quad (3.3)$$

Where E^i, n and N represent the ground state energy of individual species, total number of that particular species and total number of atoms present in the system, respectively.

$$\Delta E = \frac{[E_{tot} - (8*Cs + 4*Tl + 4*(As/Sb) + 24*I)]}{40} \quad (3.4)$$

The obtained ΔE values are -2.42 eV and -2.39 eV for Cs₂TlAsI₆ and Cs₂TlSbI₆, respectively. Also, we have calculated the phonon band structure of Cs₂Tl(As/Sb)I₆ as shown in figure 3.2. It is evident figure 3.2 that no imaginary frequencies exist throughout the entire Brillouin zone of both systems.

Figure 3.2: The phonon band structure of (a) Cs₂TlAsI₆ and (b) Cs₂TlSbI₆.

To clarify the phonon band structure results, we have further investigated the phonon density of states (DOS) as shown in figure 3.3 which also showed that imaginary phonon frequency is absent. Thus, $\text{Cs}_2\text{TI}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ are thermodynamically stable.

Figure 3.3: The phonon DOS of (a) $\text{Cs}_2\text{TIAsI}_6$ and (b) $\text{Cs}_2\text{TISbI}_6$.

3.2.3 Mechanical properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{TI}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$

The cohesive energy represents the difference amongst the optimal total crystal energy and sum of the constituent's bulk energies. The cohesive energy symbolizes the binding of the atoms [88]. For a stable system, atoms are in cohesion thereby energy is needed to rupture the bonds. We have computed the cohesive energy per atom. All the materials show positive cohesive energy signifies energy is needed for the dissociation of these materials into constituents, thereby advocate the stability of the materials. To perform the mechanical stability test, the elastic constants are computed. Only three elastic constants are necessary to impart the materials' mechanical stability as these materials are stable in cubic configuration. According to Born's stability criterion, the three elastic constants should not be negative, and the bulk modulus should be greater than the transversal elongation constant C_{12} , but less than the longitudinal constant C_{11} . Table 3.2 displays that the calculated C_{ij} 's values are non-negative, abide the stability conditions thereby endorse the mechanical stability of these materials [89]. Using the C_{ij} 's values other elastic parameters like the shear modulus (G), bulk modulus (B_0), Poisson's ratio (ν), Young's modulus (Y), Cauchy Pressure (C_P), Pugh's ratio (B_0/G), and Anisotropic factor (A') can be computed by using mathematical relation given in the Chapter 3. The other mechanical properties like the brittle nature, anisotropic behavior, and so on are predicted using elastic constants. The brittleness of the DPs is predicted from computed values of Poisson's ratio (ν), Cauchy pressure (C_P), and Pugh's ratio (B_0/G) [90]. The index values for these parameters are 0.26, 0, and 1.75 for ν , C_P and B_0/G , respectively. Above the index

values materials are predicted to have ductile charters. The obtained values are lower than index values, indicating that these materials are brittle. These materials have modest anisotropic nature, which is further proven by computation of the anisotropic factor (A'), which deviates slightly from unity. Additionally, confirmed by the computation of sound velocity along different directions given in Table 3.2, which deviates slightly except for Fe-based perovskite.

Table 3.2 The calculated bulk modulus (B), Elastic constants (C_{ij}), Cauchy pressure (CP), and formation energy (ΔE) of $Cs_2TI(As/Sb)I_6$.

Systems	B (GPa)	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{44}	CP	ΔE (eV)
Cs_2TIAsI_6	22.16	44.12	13.81	11.17	2.64	-2.42
Cs_2TISbI_6	20.16	37.68	11.18	9.89	1.29	-2.39

3.2.4 Electronic band structure of $Cs_2TI(As/Sb)I_6$

The electronic nature of a system can be explored from its band structure analysis. Also, the band structure can predict whether a system is semiconductor, metal or semimetal. In addition, many physical properties such as resistivity, conductivity, effective mass, mobility and optical properties of a material can be predicted from the band structure of a material. Therefore, the band structure of $Cs_2TI(As/Sb)I_6$ is calculated. It is worthy to mention here that the new mBJ functional can provide the electronic band gap of a lead-free double halide perovskite close to its experimental value [90]. For instance Samah et al have calculated the band gap of $Cs_2LiY(Br/I)_6$ with new mBJ approach and obtained their gap values close to exact results . Therefore, the band structures of $Cs_2TI(As/Sb)I_6$ are calculated with same approach which are shown in figure 3.4 (a, b). It is noticeable from figure 3.4 (a, b) that valence band maxima (VBM) and conduction band minima (CBM) of $Cs_2TI(As/Sb)I_6$ are located at the same k-point implies they are direct band type materials. The direct band gap is originated due to perfect matching of the electronic configuration of Tl^+ [$6s^2$] and $(As/Sb)^{3+}$ [$4s^2$]. Also, the detailed analysis revealed that the band gap (E_g) of 1.10 eV and 1.33 eV for Cs_2TIAsI_6 and Cs_2TISbI_6 , respectively. It is important to mention here that the band gap of both systems is within the range of 0.9 eV – 1.60 eV which is required for the construction of high efficiency solar cells.

Figure 3.4: The band structure of (a) $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ (b) $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$ obtained by using the new mBJ functional.

The parabolic fitting of band structures provides the effective masses of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$. We have obtained the carrier effective masses m_e^* (m_h^*) of $0.15m_0$ ($0.17m_0$), and $0.16m_0$ ($0.19m_0$) for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$, and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively. The calculated effective masses are summarized in table 3.3.

Table 3.3 The calculated effective masses of electron (m_e^*) and hole (m_h^*) of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$.

Systems	m_e^* (m_0)	m_h^* (m_0)
$\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$	0.15	0.17
$\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$	0.16	0.19

3.2.5 Electronic band structure of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$

To clarify the band structure results, the density of states (DOS) of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ are evaluated. Figure 3.4 (a) and figure 3.5 (b) exhibited the DOS results of $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively. It is noticeable from figure 3.4 (a) that the valence band of $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ range from -2.02 eV to 0 eV is mainly contributed by I-p. Similarly, figure 3.5 (b) clearly showed that the valence band of $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$ range from -2.26 eV to 0 eV is mainly contributed by I-p orbital. On the other hand, CBM of both systems is contributed by (As/Sb)-p. Thus, the possible electronic transition takes place from I-p orbital to (As/Sb)-p orbital. This electronic transition is responsible for the modification of optical properties.

Figure 3.5: The DOS of (a) $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$, and (b) $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$ obtained with the new mBJ.

3.2.6 Optical properties

Figure 3.5 (a) exhibited the frequency dependent real and imaginary dielectric constant spectrum. The imaginary dielectric constant (ϵ_2) reflects the phenomena of electronic transition from valence to conduction bands. The threshold energy needed for electronic transition is known as the optical band gap. It is clearly noticeable from figure 3.6 (a) that the optical band gap of $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$, and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$ are 1.13 eV and 1.31 eV, respectively. It is worthy to mention here that the optical band gap values of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$, are close to their electronic band gap. Beyond the optical band gap, there is a rapid increase of $\epsilon_2(\omega)$ with the energy of incoming EM waves. Also, the first absorption peaks of $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$, and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$ are noticed to be at 1.95 eV and 2.85 eV, respectively. The origin of absorption peaks beyond the optical band gap can be explained from partial density of states (PDOS). For instance, the first absorption peak of

$\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ is originated due to the electronic transition from valence band of I-p to conduction band of (As/Sb)-p states. We have also calculated the real dielectric constant $\epsilon_1(\omega)$ as shown in figure 3.5 (a). It is important to mention here that the polarization of light can be described from $\epsilon_1(\omega)$. Also, the real dielectric constant at zero frequency known as static dielectric constant has special importance to know about the defect tolerance capability of a system. The obtained values of $\epsilon_1(0)$ are 6.6 and 4.9 for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively. The appreciable values of static dielectric constants demonstrated that these systems have defect tolerance capability of these systems. Also, the calculated $\epsilon_1(0)$ values are consistent with Penn's model [92] i.e., $\epsilon_1(0) = 1 + (\frac{h\omega_p}{E_g})^2$. The detailed analysis reveals that $\epsilon_1(\omega)$ is negative in the energy range of 2.5 – 3.7 eV and 3.72 – 4.35 eV for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$, and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively. Thus, $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$, and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$ showed the metallic nature within the above-mentioned energy range. It is worthy to mention here that $\epsilon_1(\omega)$ becomes negative when the frequency (ω) of incoming EM waves is smaller than the plasma frequency (ω_p) of a material.

We have evaluated the absorption coefficient (α) as shown in figure 3.6 (b). It is evident from figure 3.6 (b) that $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ have higher order (10^5 cm^{-1}) of α beyond their optical band gap. The higher order (10^5 cm^{-1}) of absorption coefficient of titled systems is due to their direct band gap with suitable values. Also, we have obtained the maximum α values of $9.01 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $9.85 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively. The maximum α corresponds to the energy values of 1.99 eV and 2.79 eV, for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively. The maximum value α demonstrates the highest attenuation of incoming EM waves. Most importantly, higher order (10^5 cm^{-1}) of α beyond optical band gap demonstrated that $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ are emerging photovoltaic materials.

The optical conductivity (σ) demonstrates the conduction of charge carriers inside a material when a photon having a certain frequency falls on it. It is evident from figure 3.5 (c) that σ of $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$ become conductive when the energy of incoming EM waves is above

the optical band gap. The maximum σ values are found to be $1365 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1110 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively. The maximum σ corresponds to the energy values of 1.99 eV and 2.81 eV for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively.

We have also investigated the reflectivity (R) of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl(As/Sb)I}_6$ as shown in figure 3.5 (d). It is noticeable from figure 3.6 (d) that $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl(As/Sb)I}_6$ have low R (%) in the entire energy range up to 5 eV. The result of Energy loss (L) is shown in figure 3.6 (e) which describes the energy loss of photons while travelling through a material. The peak of L is associated with plasma resonance. The resonance energy of L is found to be 4.35 eV and 4.42 eV for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively. Altogether, the high α and σ with low R demonstrated that $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl(As/Sb)I}_6$ are promising photovoltaic materials.

Figure 3.6: The optical properties (a) $\epsilon(\omega)$, (b) α , (c) σ , (d) R, and (e) L of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl(As/Sb)I}_6$ obtained with the new mBJ approach.

3.2.7 Thermoelectric properties

We have studied the thermoelectric properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl(As/Sb)I}_6$ for 200 K-600 K. The Seebeck coefficient (S) plays an important role to describe the thermoelectric performance. Thus, we have studied the temperature variation of S as shown in figure 3.7 (a). The S is defined by the ratio of voltage difference to that of a temperature difference. It is noticeable from figure 3.6

(a) that S values of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ are decreasing with temperature. This decrease in S is because of cancellation of induced Seebeck voltage due to the movement of both types of charge carriers. It is also evident from figure 3.7 (a) that there is a similar pattern of S for both the systems. Furthermore, higher S is obtained from $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$. This difference in S can be understood in terms of band gap which is dependent on temperature and carrier concentration. It is worthy to mention here that the S is sensitive to the shape of DOS near VBM and CBM. The temperature variation can directly affect the shape of DOS. The room temperature S is noted to be $153.1 \mu\text{V K}^{-1}$ and $142.2 \mu\text{V K}^{-1}$ for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively. The overall positive value of S indicates that hole is the majority carrier in $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$. Thus, $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$ are p-type in nature. The p-type nature of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ are also supported by effective mass calculation i.e. $m_h^* > m_e^*$.

The temperature variation of σ/τ for $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ is shown in figure 3.7(b). We can see that σ/τ has a proportional relationship with temperature which describes the semiconducting nature of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$. This trend of σ/τ is consistent with band theory. Similar type of σ/τ pattern was found by Haque et al for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiX}_6$ [$X = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$] [93]. It is a well-known fact that the thermal energy can create a charge carrier inside the semiconductor. The increase of temperature can enhance the carrier concentration and corresponding electrical conductivity. The values of σ/τ at room temperature are noted to be $9.0 \times 10^{18} \Omega^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $8.6 \times 10^{18} \Omega^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$ respectively. Most importantly, the higher order of σ/τ ($10^{18} \Omega^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) implies that $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ are promising thermoelectric material.

Furthermore, we have calculated temperature variation k/τ . It is evident from figure 3.7 (c) that k/τ has a proportional relationship with temperature. Similar pattern of k/τ is proposed by Bhanu et al for Cs_2PdX_6 ($X = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$) [94]. The room temperature k/τ values are noticed to be $0.95 \times 10^{14} \text{ W/mKs}$ and $1.03 \times 10^{14} \text{ W/mKs}$ for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively. The interesting finding is the ultra-low (10^{14} W/mKs) k/τ of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$, which is required for thermoelectric technology. Motivated by high S and σ/τ with low k/τ , we have further calculated the figure merit (ZT) which is displayed in figure 3.7 (d). We observe that the ZT values of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$ are decreasing with the temperature at a very slow rate. The values of ZT at room temperature are found to be 0.757 and 0.754 for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$,

respectively. The high ZT values implies that $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$ are potential thermoelectric materials.

Figure 3.7: The temperature variation of (a) S , (b) σ/τ , (c) κ/τ and (d) ZT of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$.

3.3 Summary and Conclusion

In this chapter, we have systematically investigated the structural, electronic, optical, and thermoelectric properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$ by first principles calculation. The obtained negative formation energy of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$ along with absence of imaginary phonon frequency revealed that these two systems are thermodynamically stable. In addition, the new mBJ approach predicted the direct band gap value of 1.10 eV and 1.33 eV for $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlAsI}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{TlSbI}_6$, respectively. Furthermore, the optical studies revealed that the higher order (10^5cm^{-1}) absorption coefficient, appreciable conductivity, and low reflectivity of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$ due to their dispersed direct band nature with suitable band gap value. Moreover, the thermoelectric studies showed that the higher ZT value of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$ which is originated from the ultra-low thermal conductivity and higher electrical conductivity. Thus, $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$ are predicted to be emerging photovoltaic and thermoelectric materials.